

Lexical-semantic analysis of euphemisms in English

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Abstract. This article delves into the details about lexical-semantic analysis of euphemisms in English language.

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Early Thoughts on the Phenomenon of Euphemism in World Linguistics can be seen in the works of J.Vandries, L.A. Reformatsky. As A.A. Bulakhovsky quoted, he believes that the euphemistic units used under the taboo are related to ethnic development. He acknowledges that taboos are caused by various heresies and superstitions, and emphasizes that euphemisms serve to cover them up. Modern linguists have set a clear task to systematically study euphemisms as a speech layer as a whole to reveal all speech potential and to highlight its semantic and structural features. In this regard, this article we will try to reveal the comparative structural-semantic analysis of euphemisms in English and Uzbek on the basis of examples from works of art. In English, a phrase meaning "disabled" is analyzed as follows: Woman you have gone too far! You are out of your senses! (D. Carter)

Linguistic euphemisms are lexical units that can be lexified. For example, euphemisms such as "to do slavery," "to perish," "to be a victim," and "to leave us," which express the notion of "dying," are linguistic euphemisms. The verbal euphemism occurs mainly in the verbal context. At the heart of the term speech euphemism is the necessity, temporary taboo in the temporal speech it is a process. Therefore, it is possible to conditionally use the in terms original or absolute euphemism for linguistic euphemism and relative or temporary euphemism for verbal euphemism, because verbal euphemisms are used in the real sense of the word outside the context. Euphemisms are divided into a) verbal; and b) nonverbal euphemisms according to the means of expression. In speech process, a particular situation requires that the reality taboo can be expressed through nonverbal means, but not in verbal speech. Nonverbal means of expressing euphemistic meaning are also natural and necessary methods and play an important role as a component in the speech process. Nonverbal euphemistic speech is usually could be as: a) Conciseness, thrift and language measure; b) it is based on the situational demand of context and speech situation. Nonverbal euphemistic expressions can also be studied under the units of implicative and kinetic euphemisms. The implicative euphemism is based more on context or written speech. This process focuses mainly on presupposition, ellipse, intonation, silence, and pause. Verbal euphemism expresses the euphemistic meaning which use lexical-semantic movements and speech figures, whereas nonverbal express speech gestures facial expressions, gestures, mannerisms of the interlocutor, the speech situation and the tone associated with these processes, its elements is to work with prosodic means. It is important to note that these two means of speech are not completely isolated from each other.

In an implicit expression the structure of the sentence changes like: incompleteness, ellipticalization, as well as there will be changes in the content of the sentence. In conclusion, we can note that semantic-structural analysis of euphemisms in the comparable English and Uzbek languages is characterized by similarities, commonalities and, in turn, differences. In general, no matter what language our euphemisms are used, they serve to appeal the speech. Euphemism is an important form of language developed by people who wanted to create idealized communicative effects in the process of socializing. By using euphemism, bold or direct words can be avoided to make sure that nobody in the conversation gets hurt mentally. Euphemism is considered as lubricant applied in coordinating interpersonal relationships. It is really important and practical to know some phenomena in English euphemism from the perspective of semantics. Euphemism like —blow one’s cool|| or —blow a gasket|| all mean —angry|| in English language without directly changing the lexical meaning of the words, but these expressions are more comfort for people to receive. This exchange of unpleasant or bad-association-causing words/phrases to more comfort and pleasant ones makes euphemism unique and distinctive in semantics. Word —grave|| can be changed into euphemisms like —final resting place|| or —garden of sleep,|| thus making language more vivid and acceptable. Euphemism makes irritant words into moderate ones by using different ways of rhetorical devices, such as simile, metaphor, metonymy, and so on. As the person at the center of language and speech events, each process develops directly and indirectly through his or her speech. Speech euphemisms differ from the point of view of belonging to two opposite sexes. Euphemism is a bitter medicine in a sweet shell. Tongue euphemisms are speech actions associated with a desire to speak politely.

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With euphemisms, we can show courtesy to our interlocutor on the one hand and eliminate unpleasant moments for him. On the other hand, euphemisms represent the main content expressed allegorically. M: “you are wrong” (you are wrong, you are wrong), “do not stay away from the truth” (do not speak wrong), “this dress will look great” (old) and so on. According to the great director Sergei Eisenstein, the artist should be able to see the skull through the beautiful pink skin of the girls during the filming process. And euphemisms are just like that pink crust. No matter how beautiful it is, we always understand the meaning behind it.

In social life, family conditions and living conditions of people do not differ. There are a number of women in the society who are old but unmarried or divorced, whose husbands have died, and the words that apply to them must be very careful. The "single woman" euphemism used above applies to non-married women and helps to smoothly convey an uncomfortable notion. "Are you open?" "There's a nice guy, what do you say?" She didn't even want to answer, and nodded away at us. (talk) (husbandless). The expression "open" in this example is euphemistic and serves to describe the concept of "landless". However, it should not be used in the manner of the Uzbek speech in the form of open, dysfunctional. Holder says there are many euphemisms for the notion of "jazz". This is because a woman living with a man out of wedlock has been criticized by society. Men try to hide it through left-handed wife, little wife, lover, secretary, nephew, female-friendly euphemisms. As can be seen from the examples, most of the euphemisms that represent age do not discriminate against gender. These euphemisms can be easily applied to women and men. Because sex does not play an important role in it. Euphemisms that represent the appearance of women. Euphemisms, which emphasize the attractiveness of women, are often used by

men to hide the interests of a particular woman and help them to a certain extent.

Euphemisms related to women's beauty are a very relevant topic at the moment. Because beauty makes women to undergo any cosmetic procedures. For example, they are ready to do anything to improve their face, skin, hairstyles, and so on. However, not every woman admits that her beauty is the result of the work of cosmetologists. They cover the disadvantages of cosmetics and fall into the category of "looking after" women. In certain words, people who are at risk are found in taboos (taboo words). Pilots, paratroopers, circus artists, for example, are afraid to use the word "last." Instead, "edge" (or "one more time" is indirectly used in the circus to use the "last", "ending" or "be") units - for example, "edge flight." They also try to substitute the word "death" with "bony" and "nose-free" expressions. While gold miners use "yellow metal" instead of "gold", the same report is made of gold, as a special investigation gives a definitive conclusion on the nature and character of the seized material and is illegal before the decision to accept yellow metal as gold.

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